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SHAKESPEARE AND THE DIGITAL CREATIVE INDUSTRIES IN ROMANIA

Abstract

Recent years have witnessed the emergence of creative industries, defined by UNESCO as “the creation, industrial reproduction and mass distribution of cultural works”. Digital creative industries integrate digital cultural content and digital equipment. Our paper sets out to analyse the degree to which Shakespeare's work has been turned into digital content in Romania, the various ways in which this metamorphosis has occurred and to what extent digital Shakespeare-related content has been monetised by creative industries in Romania.

Keywords: digital creative industries, digital Shakespeare, creativity

In his work *The Creative economy. How to make money from Ideas* (2011), Howkins identifies fifteen sectors where creativity is the most important raw resource and the most valuable economic product (Howkins, 2007: 58). The need to counterbalance the effects of globalisation and deindustrialisation, turned creativity into a “dominant ‘success story’” (Campbell, 2019: x), encouraging people and governments to find novel ways of exploiting the economic potential of culture. The activities that subjected culture to an economic policy logic came to be known as creative industries, ‘those activities which have their origin in individual creativity, skill and talent and which have a potential for wealth and job creation through the generation and exploitation of intellectual property’ (Schlessinger, 2006:6-7). This paper briefly investigates the digital production and reception of Shakespeare-related content in Romania and the ways in which it was used to generate profit.

One of these sectors included among the creative industries is Performing Arts, which “include all kinds of on-stage and site-specific performances” (Howkins, 2007:70). The reception and ‘exploitation’ of Shakespeare’s texts for economic reasons would certainly revolve around the stage productions, even if one of the first and main ways of appropriating Shakespeare in Romania was through translations. As Hartley notes:

performing arts have played a central role in all cultures. Artists have ‘articulated’ the relationship between their works and society and in doing so they have institutionalised

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specific disciplinary procedures and artistic conventions. The terminology of art practices – genres, styles and conventions – has in turn shaped the institutionalisation of training, the conditions of work, perceptions of value and the marketplace for such works. (Hartley *et al*, 2013:40)

A (Romanian) misconception is that everything that is related to culture should be above the mundane financial worries, and that all the artistic and cultural fields should be left in the care of the state, but a powerfully emerging independent theatre changed the traditional artistic conventions in the country. In Scena.ro, Cristina Modreanu, a Romanian theatre critic, speaks of the parallel cultural market that has been growing in the last decade in the independent cultural sector. This sector, which already has a loyal audience, she argues, comes with a varied cultural offer and modern approach that is more receptive to change than the conservative cultural institutions of the state. However, the pandemic caught everybody by surprise and the state found itself in the impossibility to cover all personnel and maintenance costs of cultural institutions. There were cases reported in the press of actors who started side businesses such as candle making to make up for the diminished income. In an article published by an online magazine, Scena.ro, Irina Artenii, actress, qualifies 2020 as the worst possible year to graduate from a Film and Drama School. At the same time, she refuses to be part of the actor generation that moved the theatre into the virtual world. This, she says, would be another art form, another performative art that can no longer be called theatre. Anna Blacwell, in her work *Shakespearean Celebrity in the Digital Age*, dwells on this growing dissention between scholars who defend the classical idea of theatre, and those who more readily embrace the contemporary heterogeneity of visual media in performance:

Performance scholarship indeed tends to imagine the original act of live spectatorship as the best and truest form of theatre experience (something which criticism on the livestreaming of theatre is increasingly complicating). Peggy Phelan writes famously, for instance, that performance's 'only life is in the present'. Performance cannot be saved, recorded, documented, or otherwise participate in the circulation of representations: once it does so it becomes something other than performance' (Phelan 1993: 146). Hartley imagines similarly that the initial point of connection between theatre actor and audience is all but lost over time, only to be replicated in our inexact and often unreliable memories. Watching the same star on television or film might be 'less present' or potent than the connection forged in the theatre, therefore, but according to James, it may also be 'more knowable' and consequently more 'concrete and meaningful' (2007, 46). (Blackwell, 2018:104)

However, the present research has in view a type of theatre audience that does not have easy and immediate access to traditional theatrical performances, mainly due to the fact that they live too far from cultural centres where live theatre is available. Many people find themselves in such a situation, around Europe. As Howkins was noting, in 2001, about English Theatres,

The London theatres are flourishing but there is concern about the gap between the prosperous West End and the poverty of the regional theatres which, according to the Arts Council of England, have long been 'starved of nance' and are under threat of extinction. While Londoners can choose between 50 theatres, many people elsewhere may have to travel 30 miles to visit one. (Howkins, 2007:71)

Oana Cristea-Grigorescu, a Romanian theatre critic, writes for dw.com that the migration of the audience to online platforms only testifies to people's need for theatre. According to her,

“the recent years have taught us to surpass, by online theatre, the limits of the theatrical spaces that are geographically inaccessible”¹.

The pandemic incapacitated, for a while, all audiences, and institutions reacted in different ways in their attempt to deal with this period of confusion. In Moldova, the eastern part of Romania, on the webpage of the National Theatre in Iași, one could find links to the pages of all theatres in the province of Moldova, including the page of The National Theatre in Chișinău, in The Republic of Moldova. The *Mihai Eminescu* Theatre, in Botoșani, published a video recording of their 1997-1998 *Hamlet* (directed by Ion Sabdaru) in November, 2020, it has since had 432 views. The *Matei Visniec* Theatre from Suceava published a video recording of the play *Love Labour's Lost*, (directed by Alexandru Bogdan) that was available in January 2020 and in April 2021. Other recorded performances were also available at the theatre in Iași and Suceava, but the choice was obviously for open air or traditional performances. At the other extreme, the National Theatre Radu Stanca from Sibiu has proved a tremendous adaptation energy. They have a collaboration with Scenadigitala, a live streaming platform that makes the performances of the theatre in Sibiu available everywhere around the world. Unfortunately, no Shakespeare plays were present in the programme.

The research on this broad topic of the digital Shakespeare is not easily done. The existence of such streaming platforms is a must amid researchers in the field. In an article entitled *Teaching Digital Humanities in Romania*, long before the pandemic constraints were in place, Mădălina Nicolaescu and Adriana Mihai (2014) tackled on the subject of digital Shakespeare:

The centrality of Shakespeare in the humanities in Romania allows for networking with departments of Romanian and other foreign language departments within the University of Bucharest, as well as with the respective departments at the universities of Cluj, Timișoara, and Sibiu. Our goal is to set up a community of students and faculty involved in digital humanities, digital technologies in education, and the reconfiguration of Shakespeare studies in our universities in order to promote digital humanities to the forefront of scholarly debate and investigation. (Nicolaescu & Mihai, 2014:3/8)

Although such networks and the subsequent activities they generate are vital for students and researchers, these can hardly find a place among creative industries as they simply continue the long-established academic tradition and do not result in financial profit. Cojanu (2016:20) underlines, however, that the cultural and creative production can create effects that are not necessarily monetized, without a decrease in their social importance. More than that, Cojanu argues, the attempt to place a cultural product on the market, might have contrary and unexpected effects. Casey (2019: 2/19) analyses the effect of the digital cultures on the reception of Shakespeare and concludes that the consumer/creator moves away from Shakespeare's text. In the same way, Casey argues, “when such projects are migrated to the classroom, they often reveal more about the attitudes and interests of the students than they do about Shakespeare and his culture”.

On the other hand, the traditional approach to Shakespeare at both research and performance levels inhibited the absorption of Shakespeare related activities in the culture of the youth. In the same way, disregarding technological innovation in the creation and dissemination of culture will only limit cultural industries to a struggling market niche. Volintiru (2015: 292-293) pinpoints the fact that artistic and cultural activities do not always imply a commercial goal, as they are less appealing for entrepreneurial initiatives because the cultural market is not easily

¹ “perioada aceasta ne-a învățat să depășim prin teatrul online granițele accesului la spațiile teatrale inaccesibile geografic” (Cristea-Grigorescu, 2020)

accessible to new enterprises. Even in more appealing industries, such as the Romanian advertising market, Shakespeare had a short ascendance and a quick decline (Colipcă-Ciobanu, 2016).

That accounts for the fact that, scarce as they are, performance arts and other creative activities that involve digital Shakespeare related content are mainly funded or subsidised by state institutions. An example in this respect is the project *Shakespeare contemp.zoom*, a laboratory of theatrical and creative introspection created in 2020, co-financed by the independent theatre platform Arte-Factum and the Local Council of Timișoara, with a view to pave the way for the project of turning Timișoara into the European Cultural Capital in 2023 (Luculescu, 2020).

The digitisation of cultural content meets the needs of geographically distant audiences and increases accessibility to and recyclability of cultural projects, offering abundance, convenience and mobility of information and entertainment” (Hesmondalgh, 2019:118), this comes at a price. UNESCO signals the major crisis in the creative sector, where ten million jobs were lost during and, on top of that, “the increasing digitisation of the cultural output means it is harder than ever for artists to make a living” (Sherwood, 2022). While Shakespeare is still a canonical author for the academic and theatrical Romanian tradition, his work has yet to inspire the turn from a spectatorial/ static approach to a more participative/active one, that would fully exploit the digital blessings of the world economy.

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